

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: AHMAD****FIRST NAME: TANWIR****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did did *not* use Zotero to insert referencesThe author used the following software: MSOffice 365

ESSENTIAL WRITING CONCEPTS FOR ACADEMIC PAPERS

1) INTRODUCTION

As public health researcher robust write-ups on health issues, concern, approaches, and policy papers, written by researchers, academics, and professionals always intrigued me and at the same time more often appeared as a challenge. Euclid University course work in academic writing open doors to effective writing: fundamentals of academic writing, proper English (US/UK), and proper style in formatting and writing. This response paper is based on ACA-401D period one coursepack written by Cleenewerck and Gulma. It is an important coursepack for a doctoral candidate, like me. It provides foundational elements for quality driven meaningful writing. Effective writing requires systematic, grammatically correct, and proper writing style to establish claim, share evidence, and generate discussion in each paragraph in a straightforward way which is well established by Chicago-Turabian style (Macmillan and Koch Jr. 2011, 2). The coursepack is enriched by instructor led videos on Basic ACA-401D and Zotero Training.

This learning material could be divided into two parts. First part of coursepack consists of essentials of academic writing: essay writing, plagiarism, rules for writing, literature review, and style guide. Whereas, second part of coursepack deals with the nuances of American and British English, Sample corrected papers, Chicago Manual Style (CMS) crib sheet, and Latin abbreviations and expressions. Second part of coursepack complements the first part.

2) FIVE ELEMENTS OF ESSAY WRITING

The coursepack gives insights into elements of engaging and effective writing. It well connects with my experiences in documenting projects process and communicating result, and present job role in public health research. In published documents and presentations, I had experiences that well-planned succinct evidence based well-argued and counter argued write up makes sense to audience and result in meaningful communication with the key stakeholders (government departments, non-profit institutions, and community leaders). In my opinion, following five concepts of essay writing is essential for research and publications in peer reviewed international journals.

Begin Early

The beginning chapter of coursepack (EUCLID 2019, 1-4) document the essay writing materials from Writing Skills Center University of New South Wales (UNSW)¹. As required in the real work situations, Writing Support Center UNSW set purpose of good essay is to persuade reader based on evidence, and explain basic steps. It starts with define the question and analyze the task. This is matches with what I do in my work prior to writing a document for colleagues, partners, and stakeholders. But contrary to what is expected in this element, most of the time I did not carry the practice of developing initial essay plan by jotting down ideas/ thoughts/learnings points form field notes. The benefits narrated in the UNSW website that “Essay plans helps with structuring an essay.” Three core steps are: begin early, define the question and analyze the task, and write a preliminary essay plan. These three initial preparedness steps to writing a paper is a precursor of well thought over, well organized write-up. I think that adherence to this step will benefit at lot: save time, reduce hours of efforts, lower chances of leaving important part in the write up, time to recheck, and remove errors in planning and final output. However, compared with source material at UNSW, coursepack have noticeable error in spelling and some grammatical issues in copying the material from original text shown in brackets in bold fonts:

1. Starting the essay (**begin early**)
2. Writing down everything you know about a topic is not enough (**won't be enough**)
3. *The Learning Centre guide 'Answering Assignment Questions'* (**italics** not in the original text)
4. Construct an initial plan (**write a preliminary essay plan**)
5. Your response, and find some answer (not in Australian English)
6. Draw up an initial essay plan (**entire sentence is not in the original text**)
7. Write a preliminary essay plan (missing word quick... write a **quick**, preliminary plan)

¹ The Basics of Essay Writing

8. As you begin to write and research your plan will probably change (**remember, your plan at this point is provisional. As you begin to write and research it will probably change**)

Research the Topic

Literature review is vital component of research. Searching for related studies and critical gaps / issues related with topic under study will lead to formulation of thesis/ research questions and arguments to answer. The study material suggests three steps to achieve this process; Reading for the essay, generate reading list, and takes notes from reading list (referencing). To my understanding all three steps are interwoven and goes simultaneously, but largely missing in the professional writeup of public health programs. Mostly these steps are adhered and somewhat enforced in the academic institutions. Yet, in the professional writeups for community projects adequate literature reviews were often compromised for lack of time, resources, skill to apply referencing software (Zotero, EndNote), and lack of intention to access huge literature available on the web such as PubMed, Library of Congress, Lancet, Google Scholar, Universities Library's, Government web sites and many others web pages and give time to reading, taking notes, and reflecting over notes. Similar to previous section, this section in the coursepack contains some errors in *copying the original text given at UNSW, shown in brackets in bold fonts*:

1. A feature of most academic writing is that it draws on the work of other writers and researchers. Therefore, reading and researching are vital to essay writing. Researching provides the knowledge and evidence that allows you to develop a thesis and argument to answer the essay question (**italics** not in the original text)
2. When you look at your readings more closely, remember to read with a purpose. (First part of the sentence is unwanted. **Always** read with a purpose)
3. ***What do I already know about the topic?*** Start with what you know. If a topic is unfamiliar, do some introductory reading. See your lecture notes and course readings for help
4. ***What do I need to read*** to be able to answer the essay question? ***Is this material useful*** and relevant to my thesis/argument? ***How will this material further explore my argument?*** (**italics**, not in the source text)
5. Make notes from the readings (**taking notes from your readings**)
6. Take/make notes (**/make** not in the original text)
7. *Do not take notes during your first reading. Always make notes with the question clearly in mind. Note all sources of information.* (**Italics**, not in the original text)

Organize Your Ideas

This is second stage of planning an essay. At this stage rethinking goes into all the materials collected, assembled, research questions framed and how the essay will be structured. The structuring also considers any instructions/ guidelines or expectation given by the immediate audience: donor agencies, government departments, partner organizations, academic institutions, and publishers. The coursepack/UNSW webpage rightly advises students that reframe essay plan and think it though for creative and critical thinking. In practice, while documenting project process or writing program outcomes, I always think over what I should write to make sense and meet the audience requirement. But I have not made systematic efforts in planning essay second time. Hence, to me this is very important stage for improving write-up. In this section, coursepack also wrongly places italics and committed omissions. The actual text is given in brackets in bold fonts.

1. Organising Your Ideas (**organise**)
2. *Begin organising your research and ideas into answer* (sentence not in **italics**).
3. Essay plans (**write a second essay plan**)
4. After you do some research and note making, draw up a second plan (This sentence is **not in the original text**)
5. ...in terms of the research you have done) (**brackets** wrongly placed and full stop is missing)
6. ...support your answer (3rd bulleted point **full stop** at the end missing)
7. and in which order (4th bulleted point **full stop** at the end missing)
8. Write all this down in point form, and this will be your essay plan (, **and** wrongly added and **full stop** at the end missing)
9. Thinking it through (it should be **think** only)
10. *Creative thinking* (**italics** not in the original text)
- 11, *Critical thinking...* (*for example ...*) (**italics** not in the original text, **brackets** unnecessary/ not in the original text)

Write Your Essay

In common practice, I usually open a word document and finalize headings first, then started writing first draft. To my understanding this is a core or fundamental section mentioned in the first chapter of coursepack. Needless to say, though over a period more than 15 years of working in different managerial/ technical job roles I need to improve my skills to adhere with tips for effective writing and while writing goes, I should put topic sentence, supporting sentence, evidence, analysis, and a concluding sentence coherently. This is hard but once inculcated in to writing habit it will make my writings very effective, acceptable, and impactful with a large audience. Some of the mis match between original text at UNSW web page and section in the coursepack are as follows (correct one given in brackets and highlighted with bold fonts).

1. Drafting (**write a first draft**)
2. Write the first draft to try out ... (**your first draft will help you work out**)
3. A draft essay will help you work out (**not the second sentence**)

4. ... and (conjunction **and** not in the original text)
5. Once you have draft... (entire sentence is **jumbled up** from original text)
6. Structure your essay to communicate your ideas and answer the questions. (Structure your essay **in the most effective way to** communicate your ideas and answer the question)
7. Beginning sentences in the tips for effective writing – should not be in **italics**

Referencing Your Essay

Appropriate citation and bibliography are crucial component of academic writing. Reading makes a point that plagiarism is a serious offence in research papers/ essays. Citing other people work not only avoids plagiarism but also an ethical practice in research. Proper referencing contributes in building repository of evidence by synthesizing works already done or how related arguments/ subject matter was discussed and deliberated by previous researchers/ writers/ academicians.

3)OBSERVATIONS

Topics discussed in the coursepack and training videos on Zotero and configuring MS Word with the Response Paper Template is useful. In fact, using Zotero with browser connector is new to me, it is powerful personal research tool and I am excited to use it. Earlier I had some exposure with EndNote which appears difficult. However, I wish Zotero connectors should also available for Adobe Acrobat Reader to pick up title and writer's name from open PDF documents.

Turabian style referencing with recommended book is very comprehensive and extremely useful guide. But it requires time to go through it, learn, and recall while writing. To my understanding style software's are more helpful when one has basic understanding in formatting and style of particular type. There are likely occasions of confusion and errors when making in text citation and referencing or notes and bibliography. For example, if I am writing in US English and referencing materials are in another version of English and in different referencing style, then basic grounding in Turabian style will be very helpful. I also loaned "Word Source 2000: A Guide to Writing, Thinking, and Learning" from the Internet archive digital library and I find it as good ready reckoner to check basics on paragraph.

4)CONCLUSION

Coursepack in ACA-401D period one offers valuable insights on academic writings. Adhering to standard writing practices and application of one particular format and style is very important. Hence, Chicago University Press edited (2008) book entitle "Kate L Turabian's (1937) 'A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations' 7th edition" is very comprehensive, useful guide, and a valuable tool for graduate student. However, to develop mastery on using it demands consistent efforts. As

doctoral student at Euclid University I will rigorously use Turabian style to my assignments and papers. It will be great learning opportunity to professional work.

REFERENCES

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MacMillan, David, and Jr., R.T. Koch. 2011. *Introduction to Chicago – Turabian Style. Center for Writing Excellence*. University of North Alabama. <https://www.una.edu/writingcenter/docs/Writing-Resources/Introduction%20to%20Chicago-Turabian%20Style.pdf> (accessed May 15, 2020)

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